

ISOLATION, PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND ELEMENTAL EVALUATION OF CASSAVA STARCH FROM DIFFERENT LOCATIONS IN ABUJA, NIGERIA

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Received 16 July 2024; revised 12 August 2024; accepted 20 August 2024

Abstract

Cassava has been a useful source of starch over the ages. However, the location of the source of cassava tuber may affect the quality and characteristics of the starch extracted from it; hence This investigation was done to examine variations in elemental and physicochemical characteristics of starch isolated from cassava tubers harvested from different locations (Bako, Sheda, Kwaita, and Yangoji) within Kwali Area Council of Abuja, FCT, Nigeria. Starch was isolated from each of the tubers employing sodium metabisulphite solution, 1% w/v and starch extracted from all the tubers was discovered to be a crystalline, bright white powder that was non-hygroscopic. The highest and lowest yields were from Bako and Sheda with 28.95% and 21.56% respectively, all the yields are quite excellent. Bako tuber starch had the highest gelatinization temperature of 85 °C and highest water holding capacity of 27.453 mg/100 g while Yangoji tuber starch possessed the maximum bulk density of 5.0% and the maximum foam capacity of 0.667 g/cm³ and Sheda tuber starch had the highest emulsion capacity of 56.0%. Amylose and amylopectin ratios for the starches showed that Sheda tuber starch had the lowest amylose content of 15.158% while Yangoji tuber starch contained the highest amylose of 20.718% hence the starch from Sheda tuber will be the best choice for diabetics. Elemental analysis of all the starches revealed the presence of heavy metals within acceptable limits. All of the starches' physicochemical characteristics demonstrated that they are comparable to starch utilised in the food, pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and textile industries and can be employed as biomaterials in these industries.

Keywords: biomaterial, cassava, elemental, kwali; starch, physicochemical

1. Introduction

Starch is a vital energy reserve and structural component of plant cells and is a prevalent polysaccharide in such cells with distinctive functional properties. Starch finds extensive application in diverse industries, including food, pharmaceuticals, and textiles. Among the sources of starch globally, cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz), a root vegetable cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions, stands out [1]. The economic importance and versatile applications of cassava starch extraction have led to extensive research in this field and garnered considerable attention. Cassava starch extraction is a process that involves isolating starch granules from cassava tubers, renowned for their high carbohydrate content [2]. The process typically encompasses several steps, depending on the extraction techniques employed, such as peeling, washing, grating, and separating starch from other components like fibres and proteins. Proper comprehension of the composition, physicochemical characteristics, and possible uses of starch gotten from cassava has been highlighted in numerous studies. Fernandes et al., (2019) examined the impact of cultivars as well as processing conditions on some physicochemical properties of starch from cassava [3]. The researchers evaluated starch samples from different cassava varieties and observed variations in starch yield, swelling power, and pasting properties among the cultivars. This study emphasized the impact of processing parameters and genetic variables on the quality and functionality of cassava starch [4].

A research done by Ahmed et al., (2020) [5] looked at traditional extraction methods as against advanced techniques such as enzyme-assisted extraction and ultrasound-assisted extraction. The cassava starch was examined based on the impact of the methods employed. Ultrasound-assisted extraction showed higher starch yield and improved functional properties to traditional methods, while enzymes enhanced extraction efficiency. Continuous exploration of cassava starch as a valuable resource holds promise for both economic development and the diversification of starch-based products. Cassava starch extraction has gained significant focus due to its practical uses in various industries and economic significance. These research studies have contributed to the understanding of the physicochemical properties, composition, and potential applications of cassava starch [6]. Investigations into extraction methods, optimization of processing parameters, and modification techniques have yielded valuable insights. Further research is needed to address the gaps in knowledge and explore novel extraction techniques, modifications, and applications of cassava starch. These include investigating the impact of different extraction methods on starch properties, optimizing processing parameters, and fully comprehending the functional properties of cassava starch derivatives [7]. The continuous exploration and understanding of cassava starch as a valuable resource holds promise for economic development and the diversification of starch-based products.

This current research effort gives a comparative analysis of physicochemical properties and elemental analysis of starch extracted from cassava harvested in four different locations within Kwali Area Council of Abuja, Nigeria to assess their suitability for use as biomaterials in various industries and hence contribute to sustainable and value-added starch-based products.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Cassava tubers were sourced by direct harvesting from different locations within Kwali Area Council of Abuja, FCT, Nigeria i.e. Bako, Sheda, Kwaita, and Yangoji. Corn starch (BP) was used along with analar chemicals and reagents (BDH) all acquired from Sheda Science and Technology Complex, Chemistry Advanced Research Centre. Throughout the study, de-ionized water and glassware that had been acid-washed were utilized.

2.2. Methods

Isolation of starch from the cassava tubers

The tubers were cleaned under running water to remove sand and other debris and then peeled before being

chopped into small sizes respectively. About 2 liters of 1 % w/v Sodium metabisulphite solution was used to soak the chopped tubers from each location separately overnight and at room temperature. After that, the hydrated tubers were taken out and used to make a slurry by wet milling them in a laboratory blender. Each sample's paste was spread out in a huge volume of 1% sodium metabisulphite solution, and it was then repeatedly filtered through muslin cloth. After that, the suspension was centrifuged for 10 minutes at 3500 rpm to help remove the debris. The mucilage was scraped off and the supernatant was gently decanted. The procedure was carried out three times, repeatedly scraping the mucilage from each starch until a pure starch was obtained for each sample. Each location's starch was then dried in the sun and again at 60 °C in a hot air oven. It was then ground up, weighed, and kept separately in sample vials until needed for additional analysis [8].

Evaluation of Physicochemical Characteristics for each starch sample separately

After shaking a 20% weight/volume mixture of each sample in water for five mins, the pH was measured with a pH meter [9].

Foam Capacity

Modifications were made to the Omojola et al. (2012) methodology and employed to evaluate the foam capacity for each sample [10]. Using a vortex mixer (vortex 2 Genie set at shake 8) and 50 ml of distilled water, a 1 g starch sample was homogenised for 5 mins. After pouring the homogenate into a 100 ml measuring cylinder, the volume was noted after 30 seconds. The percentage increase in volume was used to express the foam capacity.

Emulsion Capacity

The methodology described by Afolayan et al., (2012) was employed for this analysis [11]. Using a vortex mixer, 1 g of each individual sample was dissolved in 5 ml of distilled water for 30 seconds. Following thorough dispersion, 5 ml of vegetable oil was progressively added, and mixing was done for an additional 30 seconds. For five minutes, the suspension was centrifuged at 1600 rpm. Straight from the tube, the amount of oil that was extracted from the sample was measured. The amount of oil emulsified and retained per gram of sample is known as the emulsion capacity.

Gelatinization Temperature

About 1 g of starch samples from the different locations was filled with 10 ml of distilled water and placed in a 20 ml beaker. Each dispersion was then heated on a hot plate. A thermometer submerged in the starch slurry was thereafter used to measure the gelatinization temperature respectively [12].

Bulk / Tapped Density

Each starch sample's bulk density was calculated using the technique outlined by Adebisi et al, (2011) with minor adjustments [12]. With a short glass funnel stem, 50 g of starch powder was added to a 250 cm³ calibrated measuring cylinder. To find the bulk density, the volume that each starch occupied was observed. Bulk density (calculated in g/cm³) was expressed by dividing the weight of sample by the volume the sample occupied. Using a ruler, the cylinder was constantly tapped to determine the tapped density until a consistent volume was achieved [11].

Browning / Charring Temperature

With slight modifications, the technique outlined by Omojola et al (2012) was employed in determining this [10]. A melting point device with a model Electrothermal 9100 was used to determine the individual browning and charring temperatures of a portion of the starch sample collected from each site.

Water Holding Capacity

To ascertain water holding capacity, Fagbohun et al. (2013) approach was applied [13]. In a centrifuge tube that had already been pre-weighed, a 5% w/v of each starch sample was diluted. The tube was agitated in a vortex mixer for two minutes respectively. Then, the supernatant was discarded, and the weight of the tube and hydrated sample together was taken. The water holding capacity of the starch was shown as the water weight bonded to 100 g of dry starch.

Determination of Amylose / Amylopectin Content

Weighed into individual test tubes were the standard (corn starch) and the four starch samples (0.1 g). Carefully, 1 cm³ of 95% ethanol and 9 cm³ of 1 mol dm⁻³ NaOH were introduced to these test tubes. After completely mixing, the test tubes were covered with foil paper. To gelatinize the starch, the samples were cooked for ten minutes in a boiling water bath and then thoroughly cooled. Ten times was the suspension diluted. For analysis, 0.5 cm³ of extract from each sample was set aside, and 0.1 cm³ of acetic acid solution and 0.2 cm³ of iodine solution were added in that order. It was filled to a capacity of 10 cm³ using 9.2 cm³ of purified water. Twenty minutes were allowed for colour development of the solution which was then read in a UV spectrophotometer at 620 nm after vortexing [14]. The percentage amylose content is calculated as shown below.

% Amylose content = {% Amylose of standard X Absorbance of sample} / Absorbance of standard

Solubility Index

The methodology outlined earlier by Michael et al (2020) was employed to calculate the solubility index of each starch sample with minor adjustments [14]. In a test tube, 0.5 g of starch sample was added to 10 ml of distilled water. This was heated for thirty minutes in a water bath that had a starting temperature of fifty degrees Celsius. After that, it was centrifuged for a further half hour at 1500 rpm. A 5 millilitre decant of the supernatant was made, and it was dried to dry weight. The solubility of each sample was determined by dividing the weight of dissolved starch in the heated solution by the percentage (%). This was done between 50°C and 90°C in temperature.

Swelling Power

The methodology outlined by Michael et al (2020) was also used to evaluate the swelling power of each sample with minor adjustments [14]. Ten millilitres of distilled water were added to a test tube containing a 0.1 g sample of starch. The mixture was heated for 30 minutes while being constantly shook in a water bath at 50 °C. To remove the supernatant, which was carefully decanted and the weight of the starch paste measured, the test tube was finally centrifuged for 20 minutes at 1500 rpm. Each sample's swelling power was determined by dividing the weight of starch paste by the Weight of dry starch sample. This was done between 50°C and 95°C in temperature.

Elemental Analysis

Heavy metals content of the four starch samples were evaluated by the AOAC method (A.O.A.C., 1990) using the atomic absorption spectrophotometer (GBC Avanta Ver 2.02 Model, Australia) equipped with air-acetylene flame [15]. Each starch sample was prepared for mineral analysis by adding 10 ml of concentrated nitric acid to 2 g sample and digested until a clear solution was obtained. After allowing the digest to cool, it was moved into a normal 100 ml flask, filled to the brim with deionised water, and kept in a polypropylene container for storage. For each of the mineral elements—cadmium (Cd), cobalt (Co), nickel (Ni), sodium (Na), calcium (Ca), iron (Fe), potassium (K), chromium (Cr), magnesium (Mg), copper (Cu), manganese (Mn), lead (Pb), and zinc (Zn) in concentrated HNO₃—four working standards (1000 ppm) and a blank were constructed. The Atomic Absorption

Spectrophotometer (AAS) was used to measure the absorbance of each element in the sample in its reference solution. Using the least squares approach to fit a straight line, the calibration curves generated for concentration versus absorbance data were statistically analysed. The concentrations of each metal in the samples were reported in milligrams per gram (mg/L).

3. Results and Discussion

The starch obtained from each of the samples was discovered to be a crystalline, bright white, non-hygroscopic powder with no scent. It also had yields ranging between 21.56 to 28.95%. The yields and physicochemical parameters of starch from cassava in various locations are shown in Table 1 below while Table 2 expresses the mineral content of each starch sample. Figures 1 and 2, respectively, display the swelling power and the solubility index profiles of the starches extracted from different cassava tubers.

As expected of pure starch, the starches produced from cassava tubers from different locations in Abuja metropolis had yield ranging between 21.56% and 28.95% which, when compared to other cassava sources of starch (as high as 33%), and corn (61.4%) [16] the yields are thought to be quite significant. The starches were bright white, crystalline, non-hygroscopic powder with no odour which is typical of pure starch.

The gelatinization temperature of the starches, is quite like the other starches gelatinization temperatures that are typically seen [17], however, that of Sheda tuber starch (60 °C) is very low when compared to others like the Bako tuber starch (85 °C). The temperature that starches may be cooked to without browning or charring is indicated by their browning and charring temperatures.

Table 1. Physicochemical profile of cassava starch from various locations in Kwali area council, Abuja.

Parameters	Bako	Sheda	Kwaita	Yangoji
Yield (%)	28.95	21.56	28.77	22.96
pH	5.3	5.01	5.07	4.77
Foam Capacity (%)	2	2	4	5
Emulsion capacity (%)	55.1	56.0	52.0	44.0
Gelatinizing Temperature (°C)	85	60	72	81
Tapped Density (g/cm ³)	0.60	0.60	0.692	0.671
Browning Temperature (°C)	235.2 – 256.0	218.6 – 233.7	226.1 – 237.4	238.3 – 259.5
Charring Temperature (°C)	271.9 – 287.3	260.3 – 280.0	268.5 – 277.2	276.1 – 291.6
Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	0.473	0.50	0.562	0.60
Water Holding Capacity (mg/100g)	27.453	27.394	24.890	27.013
Amylose Content (%)	22.174	15.158	15.290	20.718
Amylopectin Content (%)	77.826	84.842	84.710	79.282

The results of the charring / browning temperatures is in tandem with that of the gelatinization temperatures as starches that had higher gelatinization temperatures also had higher browning and charring temperatures than the others (Bako and Yangoji tuber starches) while Sheda tuber starch with the lowest gelatinization temperature equally had the lowest browning and charring temperature which is also considerably lesser than what was

recorded for tiger nut and maize starches, and others. The implication is Bako and Yangoji tuber starches are the most appropriate to be used in industries which employ starch at quite elevated temperatures as its browning and charring temperatures are fairly comparable with other starches in comparison to other results published for *Icacina trichantha*, ginger, *Anchomanes difformis* and tiger nut starch [17].

Fig. 1. Cassava starches swelling profile.

Fig. 2. Cassava starches solubility profile.

Figures 1 and 2 show the different cassava starches swelling profiles and solubility indices through temperatures ranging between 50 and 95 °C. The swelling power is extremely noticeable and shows a similar curve pattern for all the starches; the values of the swelling profile for each starch is greater than of maize starch but less than that of tiger nut, ginger, and anchovy starches [14]. The starches' swelling curve indicates a rapid and progressive increase of swelling power with an increase in temperature up to 70 °C before taking a dip down which levels off at 80 °C and remains fairly constant to the end. This signifies that all these starches can be applied successfully as a disintegrant in production of tablets because an increase in swelling power indicates that starch is well suited for application as a disintegrant in pharmaceutical industries [18].

This uniform trend for all starches' swelling power was however not so observed for their solubility profile. A significant two-level swelling rhythm can be seen in the solubility index of Bako, Sheda and Kwali tuber starches where there is a rapid increase between 50 and 60 °C, followed by a steep decrease up to 70 °C, a sharp rise, and then another swift decrease starting at 80 °C while that of Yangoji increased up to 70 °C and then followed by a decrease. These demonstrate the granules' different abilities to absorb water while being heated. Two levels of inside bonding forces which relax at various temperatures have been suggested as the cause of the observed patterns and are similar to what has been observed for other starches like *Anchomanes difformis*, tiger nut, *Ipomoea trichantha*, ginger [13].

The starches from all the samples were observed to have quite low amylose content especially those of Sheda (15.158%) and Kwaita (15.290%) which will likely make such starches a better choice for diabetics and other people who are monitoring their health [14].

From the findings of this research work, all the starches had very high emulsion and foam capacities which are a bit higher than what has been generally reported for starches from other sources [11] except Bako and Sheda tubers which had a bit lower foam capacity. This can be attributed to high fat or protein content which may be from the source (parent material) [19].

The water absorption capacity of all the samples is quite high and comparable to others earlier reported [20], this also attests to the high swelling power of the starch samples. There's a likely difference in amount of amorphous to crystalline regions inside the starch granule which may be the cause of the variance in water absorption capacity between the starches. Tapped / bulk densities of all starches analysed fall within the range suggested for maize starch and are consistent with the results of others [21]. This demonstrates the starch's excellent compressibility.

Table 2: Elemental analysis of cassava starch from different locations in Kwali Area council, Abuja.

Metals	Concentration (mg/L)			
	Bako	Sheda	Kwaita	Yangoji
Nickel (Ni)	0.04	0.046	0.043	0.044
Sodium (Na)	5.58	5.58	5.55	5.32
Calcium (Ca)	16.45	10.36	7.78	7.87
Iron (Fe)	0.92	6.13	0.83	3.73
Potassium (K)	3.39	3.7	1.94	9.43
Chromium (Cr)	0.014	0.017	0.014	0.013
Lead (Pb)	0.0051	0.0054	0.0055	0.005
Zinc (Zn)	0.08	0.11	0.07	0.09
Magnesium (Mg)	5.35	7.65	1.83	5.65
Copper (Cu)	ND	0.69	ND	1.26
Cobalt (Co)	ND	ND	ND	ND
Cadmium (Cd)	0.00025	ND	0.0015	0.0033
Manganese (Mn)	0.37	0.83	0.46	1.44

The presence of nutritive metals (like potassium, magnesium, iron, sodium and calcium) in the samples was all

within the recommended dietary allowance while toxic metals (like lead, cobalt and cadmium) were either not detected or within permissible limits [22].

4. Conclusions

Starches from a variety of cassava tubers have been isolated, and some of the physicochemical characteristics have been studied. According to the study, these characteristics are quite favourable when compared to those of other starches. Cassava is a good source of starch, and the study has consequently demonstrated that starch extracted from cassava tubers grown in various locations in Abuja metropolis is a promising biomaterial for industrial usage (especially for pharmaceutical and food industries because of the excellent swelling power and low amylose content).

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